

18TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON CHEMISTRY AND THE ENVIRONMENT

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11 – 15 JUNE 2023 VENICE, ITALY

Venue:

SCIENTIFIC CAMPUS

CA' FOSCARI UNIVERSITY OF VENICE (ITALY)

Book of Abstracts

Dear colleagues,

On behalf of the Executive Board of the European Chemical Society, I wish you a warm welcome to this 18th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment. The European Chemical Society – in short EuChemS – is an overarching society at the European level with over 50 national member societies as members. In this way, EuChemS represents approximately 130,000 chemists from all over Europe. Did you ever realize that by being a member of your national society, you are a member of EuChemS too?

The slogan of this conference is 'Towards a pollution free society', which is well aligned with activities from EuChemS. The European Commission recently set up the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform and EuChemS was invited to join. The platform will effectively mainstream the zero pollution agenda by bringing together stakeholders and experts of different policy areas, including health, agriculture, research and innovation, transport, digitalization and the environment. EuChemS will emphasize to address the Zero Pollution challenges from the chemistry perspective in a science-based approach.

I am here in the Netherlands, but you are in the beautiful city of Venice, that I am sure will inspire you to have fruitful and constructive discussions on how to get to zero pollution and how to address many other challenges to create a sustainable environment. I wish you a very enjoyable conference!

Floris Rutjens

President of the European Chemical Society (EuChemS)

Do Microplastics Enhance Toxicity of 4-MBC?

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The 4-methylbenzylidene camphor (4-MBC) is one of the most commonly used organic UV filter in personal care products. Since 2022, it is identified as an endocrine disruptor with significant toxicological potential. Hence, 4-MBC related adverse effects are attracting growing concerns nowadays. Bearing in mind the physicochemical properties of 4-MBC, it could be expected to easily adsorb on microplastics surface due to their ubiquitously presence in the environment. Therefore, microplastics might act as carriers that alter 4-MBC toxicity. However, despite the widespread occurrence of these compounds within the aquatic environment, the possible human toxicity of adsorbed 4-MBC on different kinds of plastics has not been investigated yet. MRC-5 cell line, human embryonic lung fibroblasts, was used to examine the effects of 4-MBC, alone or adsorbed on polyvinyl chloride (PVC), on the cell viability using MTT assay. The tested samples (PVC, 4-MBC, as well as adsorbed samples) were used as extracts, according to ISO 19003-5 guidelines. The samples were resuspended in the cell medium (DMEM/F12) and left on a shaker for 24 hours at 37 °C to desorb. Afterwards, samples were centrifuged and the supernatant was used for treating the cells. Based on the obtained results 4-MBC showed non-linear cytotoxicity when cells were treated with alone UV filter in concentration 1 µM (68.04%), 5 µM (69.48%) and 10 µM (88.52%). The same concentrations of 4-MBC were used in adsorbed samples. Also, 4-MBC adsorbed on PVC expressed non-linear dose-response dynamics (68.44%, 61.54% and 104.30%, respectively). 4-MBC alone or in combination with PVC exerted U-shape nontraditional dose-response curve suggesting that 4-MBC might have more potent effects at low doses. Moreover, 4-MBC adsorbed on PVC showed the increased toxicity compared to 4-MBC alone. Hence, microplastics might act as carriers that adsorb, concentrate and increase 4-MBC toxicity. The study presents the first report on the cytotoxic effects of UV filters adsorbed on plastics on human fibroblast cell line.

Acknowledgement: This contribution is based upon work from COST Action CA20101 "Plastics monitoring detection Remediation recovery"- PRIORITY, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology), www.cost.eu, and by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia [grant number 142-451- 3120/2022-01].

References

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